

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278683476>

Development of New Wet Digestion Method for Extraction of Diatom from Visceral Material

Article · September 2013

CITATIONS

0

READS

729

5 authors, including:

Munish Kumar Mishra

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences

64 PUBLICATIONS 149 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Lav Kesharwani

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences

43 PUBLICATIONS 82 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

A. K. Gupta

National Geophysical Research Institute

134 PUBLICATIONS 1,669 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Amarnath Mishra

Amity University

116 PUBLICATIONS 1,043 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Development of New Wet Digestion Method for Extraction of Diatom from Visceral Material

Mishra, M. K. ,* Gupta, A. K., Vinayak, V., Kesharwani, L. and Mishra, A.

Sam Higginbottom Institute of Agriculture Technology and Science,
Allahabad, U.P., India

*Corresponding Author: munish_eureca@yahoo.com

Abstract

Diatom are unicellular photosynthesizing algae have a siliceous cell wall and are found in almost every aquatic environment. Diatom identification after digestion of visceral material in solving doubtful cases of drowning/dumping in forensic science is very important task. In this study new digestion mixture ($HNO_3:KMnO_4:H_2O_2$) in 4:2:3 ratio was utilized for digestion of visceral material (Liver, Kidney and Bone marrow). After comparison and standardization of new digestion mixture with other methods, it was found that new digestion mixture was less time consuming and capable of removing unwanted material over slide for identification of diatoms.

Key words: diatom, digestion mixture, identification

Introduction

Diatoms are unicellular photosynthesizing algae; they have a siliceous skeleton (frustule) and are found in almost every aquatic environment including fresh and marine waters, soils, in fact almost anywhere, in moist environment. Diatom occupy an important group of eukaryotic microorganisms on earth and are probably well in excess of 10,000 species (Mann *et al.*, 1999), either free-floating, planktonic forms or attached to a substrate, Benthic forms that have 2 μ m to 1mm in size, (Warner 1997). Diatoms grow as single cells, or form simple filaments/colonies. They form the base of aquatic food webs in marine and fresh water habitats. Diatoms are

divided into two orders. The Centrales (now called the Biddulphiales) which have valve striae arranged basically in relation to a point, an annulus or a central areola and tend to appear radially symmetrical, and the Pennales (now called Bacillariales) which have valve striae arranged in relation to a line and tend to appear bilaterally symmetrical. The valve face of the diatom frustule is ornamented with pores (areolae), processes, spines, hyaline areas and other distinguishing morphological features. It is these skeletal features, which are used to classify and describe diatoms, which is an advantage in terms of paleontology, since the same features are used to define extant species as extinct ones. Digestions of

visceral material are most important in relation to identification of diatom morphology. Some time diatom identifications become more difficult in presence of undigested and unwanted material. Acid digestion method of visceral material takes more time and may affect the siliceous cell wall of diatoms and may give poor result in identification. Hence new method is needed to be developed for identification.

Material and Method

Collection of Biological Sample (Visceral Samples)

Biological sample of 60 different cases related to suspected drowning/dumping were collected from postmortem house between March 2008 to February 2011 and persevered in saturated solution of normal saline.. Before collection in glass jar, it was washed with distilled water, 3-4 times and dried. Approximately 100-500g of visceral sample was taken in a jar, and then sealed with appropriate tag, labeled with date, season and month. After collection, the samples were brought to the laboratory for extraction and identification of diatoms.

Extraction of Diatoms from visceral sample

For the extraction of diatoms from biological sample several methods of digestion have been reported (Ming *et al*; 2006, Auer 1988, Li *et al*; 1999) such as Soluene-350, Proteinase-K, and Acid Digestion, Nitric Acid in disorganization Can. In the present study, the extraction of diatoms from visceral material was tried by Nitric Acid: KMnO_4 : H_2O_2 in the ratio of 4:2:3 as new digestive method for biological sample. Firstly the biological sample were taken in a glass tray and washed with distilled water. After that it was placed in a clean beaker of 1.0 liter capacity, added 400ml of distill water, 100ml of concentrated HNO_3 , 50ml KMnO_4 and 75ml of H_2O_2 were added in the beaker and placed over low flame for digestion. The new digestion method was validated by performing the above described acid digestion methods, simultaneously for the comparative extraction of diatom.

After complete digestion, beaker was covered with aluminum foil and allowed to stand overnight for settlement of the sediment. Next day with the help of dropper, sediment was taken from the bottom in a centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 1000-1500 rpm for 5-8 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and pellet in centrifuge tube was taken for slide preparation of diatoms

and examination their morphological feature for identification.

Examination of Diatoms

Slides of pellets were prepared by putting a drop of diluted pellet on the microscopic slide and left it on hot plate for drying. Finally mounted with DPX and after fixing, identification was done under the microscope at different magnifications for the presence of diatoms.

The identification was done according to standard International methods in which the following parameters were considered such as Frustules diameter, raphe (centric, excentric), pseudoraphe, semi cells, number of rows of punctate, striae diameter, valve length, breadth, symmetry (Convex, concave & straight) and their morphology and presence of band described by (Metzeltin *et al.*, 2005 Vinayak 2012).

Result and Discussion

Table: 1 Comparative result of conventional and new digestion mixture method

S.N.	Methods	Digestion time (hrs) for Kidney of 20 g	Digestion time (hrs) for Bone marrow of 20 g	Clarity of diatom under Microscope at 45x
1	Acid digestion	2:48 ± 6:25	2:05 ± 8:48	
2	HNO ₃ :KMnO ₄ :H ₂ O ₂	2:20 ± 5:37	1:55 ± 6:33	

Result observed is reported in Table -1 the digestion method described by Mei Ming *et al* (2006) was followed for comparison along with new digestion mixture. The new digestion mixture viz. HNO₃: KMnO₄: H₂O₂

gave better result as it takes lesser time than proteinase K, Nitric Acid disorganisation Can and Soluene 350 for extraction from visceral samples (Liver, Kidney and Bone marrow). In the present study visceral

Samples were digested by mixture, $\text{HNO}_3:\text{KMnO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ in 4:2:3 ratio was found to be better in terms of time taken, clarity and having lesser contaminations of other undigested organic matter. After analysis of 60 cases, it was found that new wet digestion mixture gave best result with 93.33 % (in 56 cases) and better 6.66% (in 4 cases) on the other hand conventional method gave better result with 78.33%(in 47 cases) and poor with 21.66 (in 13 cases), in respect of removal of unwanted residue and clarity in morphological study under microscope at 10x to 45x magnification. In respect of digestion time, new digestion mixture took less time for all visceral material such as kidney and bone marrow as compare to conventional methods.

Conclusion

References

1. Auer, A. (1988). Qualitative Diatom Analysis as a Tool to Diagnose Drowning. *American Journal of Forensic Medicine & Pathology*. 12(3): 213-218.
2. Li, Y., Hu, C., Chengxing, W. and Xu, W. (1999). Development of Can for Destruction of Organic Material in use for Forensic Diatom Examination. *Forensic Science International*. 101(3): 163-166.
3. Mei Ming., Xiangzhi, Meng and Enyin, Wang. (2006) Evaluation of four digestive methods for extracting diatoms. *Forensic Science International*
4. Mann, D. G., Hoek, C., Van-den, and Jahns, H. M. (1999). Algae: An introduction to phycology. *Cambridge University Press*, UK.
5. Metzeltin, D., Lange-Bertalot, H. and Garcia-Rodriguez, F. (2005). Diatoms of Uruguay. Taxonomy-Biogeography-Diversity. *Iconographia Diatomologica*. 15: 726.
6. Vinayak Vandana.(2012) Diatom Atlas of Fresh Water Bodies from Haryana (India): Diatom Atlas Lap Lambert Academic Publishing. Germany.1-104
7. Werner, D. (1997). Introduction with a Note on Taxonomy. *University of California Press*, Berkeley and Los Angeles, 498.

In the present study sixty visceral samples of different dead bodies were taken from the postmortem house and brought to the laboratory for analysis of diatom through acid digestion method as conventional method as well as by new digestion method. After standardization and examination it was found that new digesting mixture is more convenient, faster as compare to the conventional methods. Therefore, it may be concluded that the extraction of diatom from visceral material new digesting method is very useful in regards to the time saving and removal of unwanted residues on slide for getting clear morphological features of diatom.